

RISK ATTITUDES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON PSYCHOGRAPHIC PROFILES:

Gender Differences in Longitudinal Sociological Data from Bulgaria (2012–2023)

Rossen Nentchev Koutelov

Doctor of Sociology

Department of Economic Sociology, Faculty of General Economics

University of National and World Economy — Sofia

Progress Consult (est. 1996)

ORCID: 0009-0002-2841-8292

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Abstract

The central problem of the modern information society has become the question of how an individual can cope with the information avalanche in order to function successfully. The methodology for defining psychographic profiles has shown that a person activates an automated mechanism: the valves of their communication channels admit primarily that information which most closely corresponds to their essence as a personality. The population is segmented into four groups that are clearly distinguished from each other and include individuals with similar psychographic characteristics.

These groups are constant in type, but long-term consecutive studies have demonstrated that their proportional shares within the population can vary. Particularly significant proved to be gender differences in the dynamics of risk attitudes under the pressure of strongly negative processes and phenomena in certain periods. Knowledge of the principles of such transformations facilitates both economic entities and other social structures in building more effective communication toward desired recipients.

Keywords: *psychographic profiles, gender, risk attitudes, communication, information society, longitudinal research, sociological segmentation, Bulgaria, COVID-19, migration crisis*

Introduction

To cope with the information flood, human beings have activated an automated mechanism for protecting their consciousness: the valves of their communication channels admit primarily that information which most densely corresponds to their essence as a personality, while retaining the rest outside — as if behind a dam. The methodology for defining psychographic profiles (Koutelov, 2024) has shown that the population can be segmented into several groups, each of which contains individuals with very similar traits [1].

The accumulated longitudinal data have shown, however, that while the groups according to psychographic profiles — as defined through this specific methodology — are stable in number and in the personal structure of their characteristics, their proportional shares within the population can vary. It is logical that the search in this direction should start from the most basic possible grouping — and that is differentiation by gender. The level of risk propensity in the two sexes proved susceptible to the influence of significant processes and phenomena of a negative character. Longitudinal sociological studies over the years have shown that the plasticity of psychographic profiles does indeed carry the shadow of gender.

1. Sociological Approaches to the Study of Gender

Examining men and women from a sociological perspective requires analysis of social roles, expectations, power relations, and — particularly — gender inequalities. The functionalist approach focuses on the role of gender as a necessity for establishing stability in society. This presupposes that the division of social roles (in this case — gender roles) contributes to the more effective functioning of social systems: 'First, as a boy, he must learn that it is expected of a man, when he "grows up", to become the incumbent of an occupational role, to "work", to "earn a living", and very likely to support a family. He learns that the occupational system is hierarchically graded, and that if he is properly ambitious for "success", he should strive to rise toward the upper levels of that system.' (Parsons, 1991, p. 161) Such a construction emphasizes the socialization of the male toward the work role and expresses the expectation that women should identify with the maternal role.

The interactionist approach focuses on the role of social interactions in creating gender identity: 'What the human nature of males and females really consists of, then, is a capacity and a willingness to provide and to read depictions of masculinity and femininity and a willingness to adhere to a schedule for presenting these pictures, and this capacity they have by virtue of being persons, not females or males.' (Goffman, 1979, p. 8) Relatively close to this approach is the focus on the social actions of the two sexes in general: 'Gender is not a set of traits, nor a variable, nor a role, but the product of a sort of social doing. It is a situated accomplishment: the local management of conduct in relation to normative conceptions of appropriate attitudes and activities for particular sex categories.' (West & Zimmerman, 1987)

In the theory of 'hegemonic masculinity', the positions of the two sexes are clearly presented, with the male defined as dominant: 'Hegemonic masculinity is the configuration of gender practice which embodies the currently accepted answer to the problem of the legitimacy of patriarchy, which guarantees (or is taken to guarantee) the dominant position of men and the subordination of women.' (Connell, 1995, p. 77) The feminist approach focuses even more sharply on patriarchy and inequality, opposing role stereotypes. One of the foundational voices of the feminist approach, Simone de Beauvoir, states: 'Humanity is male and man defines woman not in herself but as relative to him; she is not regarded as an autonomous being.' (Beauvoir, 1956, p. 143) Pierre Bourdieu adds: 'Male domination is so rooted in our collective unconscious that we no longer even see it.' (Bourdieu, 1998)

The Marxist approach connects the emergence of private property with patriarchy and the subordination of women (Engels, 1884). Detailed examination of gender extends to

differences in behavior and communication. The latter is particularly important from the perspective of the fundamentally new conditions in which the individual exists in the dimension of the information society. Research on linguistic differences concludes that men communicate more directly and competitively, while women emphasize cooperation and emotional connection: 'For most women, the language of conversation is primarily a language of rapport: a way of establishing connections and negotiating relationships... For most men, talk is primarily a means to preserve independence and negotiate and maintain status in a hierarchical social order.' (Tannen, 2013, p. 57)

The review of the main approaches reveals a high degree of commonality — connected to the concept of inequality and domination. One of the factors that is unambiguously essential for achieving distinction over others is the degree of risk-taking. The one who takes higher risk has a greater chance of flying at maximum speed, diving deepest, climbing highest, winning the most. This is why the degree of propensity for risk-taking (or its opposite: firm attachment to security above all) is part of the construction of the methodology for defining the psychographic profiles of the population. Whether a gender differentiation exists at this point, and how stable these ratios are, is a question with direct relevance to communication.

2. Dynamics in the Proportional Shares of Groups According to Psychographic Profiles

The very first results from the application of the methodology for defining psychographic profiles of users appeared to shatter the thesis of functionalism and especially the widely held claim that gender is biologically predetermined and therefore unchangeable. Synthesizing the position of supporters of this claim: 'The most familiar explanation for the origin of our depictions of gender is, of course, the biological one. It is assumed that gender is an extension of our animal nature, and that just as animals express their gender, so do human beings: it is said that innate elements explain behavior in both cases.' (Goffman, 1979, p. 3)

Data from the series of consecutive nationally representative sociological surveys of the adult population of Bulgaria, at the first stage of applying the methodology, invariably showed one particularity: among women, a larger proportional share of representatives of the Seekers psychographic group was registered (Koutelov, 2024) — the group distinguished by its higher degree of risk propensity compared to the representatives of other psychographic profiles [2].

Moreover, these results appeared to lend support to the feminist approach in the sociological view of gender. An objective basis for postulating that the rejection of the suppression of women in patriarchal society would emancipate them and allow them to take on roles previously considered purely 'male' was provided by the gigantic civilizational changes of the second half of the 20th century. Even an eminent sociologist such as Ulrich Beck — who argued persuasively that women had still not taken their rightful place due to men's stubborn resistance — made the objective conclusion that 'Without doubt, in some central dimensions of the lives of young women, new possibilities of freedom have opened up in comparison with the generation of their mothers in the areas of law, education and sexuality, but also in professional self-realization.' (Beck, 2013, p. 186)

These changes overturned perceptions of the traditional roles of the sexes. The gradual weakening of patriarchalism as a social principle could be interpreted as a new distribution of roles — one moving in the direction of equalization and convergence of the roles exercised by both sexes. This process was not marked by interruptions; on the contrary, its dynamics methodically increased. In Germany in 1982, among management staff with the right to issue orders, only 2.7% were women (Beck, 2013, p. 181). By 2023, the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy in Bulgaria established in its regular report on gender equality that the share of women in managerial positions had reached 42% of all managers, and more specifically, among employers their share was 30% (MLSP, 2024).

Given such a clearly expressed and strengthening trend of redistribution of functions in society, it seemed that a fundamental problem noted by sociology should be lastingly resolved.

And insofar as we are dealing with changes affecting the very essence of the individual, some of the registered basic differences between men and women should be dissolving. Risk propensity has always been highlighted as categorically much more characteristic of men. The cited data appeared to prove precisely this: that the new role of women had led to a transformation of some of their essential traits — that they had embarked on the path from the sphere of security (guardian of the family hearth) toward the sphere of risk (hunter-warrior, equal to men). And exactly when this seemed to be an established and lasting fact, the direction dramatically reversed.

In the period from 2015 to 2018, a trend of decrease in the proportional share of the Seekers group among women was observed, connected to a reduction in their risk propensity. In 2017, this share fell below the corresponding share among men, and by 2018 it had contracted more noticeably, considerably increasing the distance from men.

It is completely unnecessary to seek any social activities that would have led to a new opposition between the sexes, or some aggression causing a return to male domination. The reasons for the retreat from risk behavior can be found in situations of obvious and direct danger. During the period under examination, the Bulgarian population was subjected simultaneously to two heavy influences, which were intensified by the fact that they were both internal and external — practically placing the individual in a rather helpless position, unable to 'see light' in any direction. It must be clearly and unambiguously noted that the awareness of the presence of danger here was connected to the very existence of the individual — not a danger of the nature of a financial crisis, which can be severe but does not directly threaten life.

The main phenomenon generating a sense of danger and insecurity was the migration crisis. It became a problem for all of Europe, but it particularly affected Bulgaria — as the actual border of the continent, it literally played the role of a barricade and buffer, suffering considerably more damage than 'inner-European' states. The extremely negative impact this crisis had on the Bulgarian population aroused concern even among official institutions, as evidenced for example by the position of one of the main trade union organizations: 'The fear psychosis, existing in a number of border regions (and quite realistically justified), is already spreading to the interior of the country, with the increasingly frequent security breaches at Bulgarian borders and criminal incidents involving refugees and illegal residents.' (CITUB, 2016) A definition such as 'fear neurosis' among the population in such an official document is something extraordinarily rare and testifies to a genuinely very serious problem pervading the very essence of the individual.

This explains why in principle among the population the desire to experience security increased and the propensity for risk behavior decreased — but as the data show, this reduction was much more pronounced among women. The explanation for such a difference can be found in the registered differentiation between sexes in the degree of anxiety and assessment of danger. Data from a nationally representative sociological survey showed that 60% of adult residents considered refugees a threat, with the share of those among women who did not perceive refugees as a threat to themselves being 10% less than the analogous share among men (Kyuchukov, 2016). A higher degree of personal fear among women naturally leads automatically to a greater desire for security and the evaporation of the desire to take risks.

3. Uniformity of the Direction of Change as a Consequence of the Uniformity of the Nature of the Impact

Was the negative change in the share of Seekers among women, based on their reduced desire to take risks, a coincidental or at least temporary deviation from the general trend toward the repositioning of women in society? This question seems logical, insofar as in 2019 a univocal return of this share to levels customary before the development of the migration crisis was registered. The share of women willing to take risks once again surpassed the

corresponding share among men. However, this proved to be an extremely short-lived phenomenon, which received a resounding blow the following year.

The processes and phenomena from 2020 onward have such a markedly negative character that they only widened the scissors further in the shares of the Seekers group between women and men. Despite a slight shift toward a more balanced state in the last two years, there are still no prospects for a rapid and confident return to the ratios registered before 2014. The reasons are once again complex: external and internal, generating fear for personal survival and personal social well-being.

The first — and particularly heavy — brick in the construction of this fear was the COVID-19 pandemic. Beyond the extensive information that sufficiently terrorized the consciousness of the population in most countries, the Bulgarian population was specifically pressured by the institutionalization of the presentation of the crisis. Every morning, Bulgarians awoke not with vitality, optimism, and hope, but with reports of death, scrupulously delivered with a sepulchral intonation by the established crisis headquarters. And to make things still heavier — a general was designated as the head and spokesperson of this headquarters, to lend sufficient hierarchical authority to the statements.

In such an information atmosphere, it was inevitable that a new and even stronger fear would take hold of the population. It emerged, however, that — paraphrasing George Orwell — 'All fear, but some fear more.' Equal before the probability of being killed by the lurking virus, men and women did not react in the same way: once again among women, in greater measure, the propensity for risk evaporated. This became even more strongly apparent as fear among the population was abundantly fertilized by ever new events and processes. The war between Russia and Ukraine that broke out in 2022 followed on the heels of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the following year the absolute maximum of the difference in Seekers shares between women and men was registered. Internally, processes were anything but conducive to positive change: the political crisis reached such dimensions that in the course of 4 years, parliamentary elections were held 7 times (Parliament, 2025).

The analyzed changes in attitude toward emergent dangers are not a 'Bulgarian patent.' The most telling evidence is the attitude of the sexes toward COVID-19 vaccination. In June 2021, the US Centers for Disease Control reported that vaccinated women outnumbered vaccinated men by 9.5 million, being a full 10 percentage points ahead. Experts explain this gap through complex behavioral and ideological differences between women and men. Even more striking is the neglect of gender differentiations in most European countries, given that both sociological surveys and statistical analyses contain clear warnings about possible significant differences. For example, a special analysis based on data from 61 European and OECD countries unambiguously concludes that 'Women use preventive care more often than men. They also have higher general, as well as specific, risk perceptions of COVID, and tend to see COVID-19 as a serious health problem to a greater extent than men.' (Varbanova, Hens, & Beutels, 2024) A large-scale study across all EU member states and the UK reveals dramatic gender differences in the mental health impact of the pandemic: '83% of women versus 36% of men report a significant increase in depression; 53% of women versus 37% of men report a significant negative impact on their mental health.' (Ambrosetti, 2021)

Many authors unite around the view that this remarkable difference in behavior is conditioned by the different degree to which men and women are inclined toward risk. Abundant statistical data and surveys invariably demonstrate men's higher practical readiness to accept risky actions: men in the USA are involved in fatal automobile accidents 3 times more often than women; male pedestrians in the UK are involved in accidents 80% more often than women; male drivers in the USA far more often than women start moving at a yellow traffic light; even a study among children unambiguously shows differentiation in risk assessment, with girls tending to avoid risky situations at any probability of presumed injury, while boys orient themselves to avoid risky situations only if the possible presumed injuries are assessed as severe — leading the authors to conclude that 'Males voluntarily engage in risky behaviors more often than females.' (Harris & Jenkins, 2023)

In the presented dynamics of the difference in Seekers shares among women and men — the group most inclined toward risk according to the applied methodology for defining psychographic profiles — yet another distinct tendency is observed, further underscoring the character of the change. Parallel to the fall in the share of women entering the Seekers group, a diametrically opposite process unfolds: a pronounced increase in the share of women entering the Bearings group. One of the foundational features of this group is that its representatives are the most cautious in society — that they literally turn their backs on any form of risk, preferring to 'attach' themselves to some entity (economic or social) in order to feel secure and avoid the dangers of any kind of risk. The dynamics in both groups unambiguously show that what was observed was not merely a decrease in risk propensity, but a literal swing from one pole to the other — demonstrating the shattering character of the process.

Conclusion

The changes in the proportional shares of groups according to psychographic profiles among men and women under the influence of strong negative processes and phenomena is an evident fact. As one of the most probable reasons for it, the gulf between the two sexes in risk assessment and in the undertaking of actual risk behavior emerges clearly. This conclusion provides grounds for successfully predicting similar changes in the shares of individual profiles — which is important from the perspective of economic and other social entities seeking the most effective messages through which to reach desired recipients.

A separate question is whether, over a longer time span, this characteristic will be preserved. The girls who were young when Ulrich Beck analyzed the positive changes among them compared to their mothers (1986) were already grandmothers in 2016. At least three generations of women have thus been realizing themselves under conditions that are new for their gender, smoothing out the edges of their differences with men. Whether this period is still insufficient for a change both in the roles of women and in their basic essence — or whether there are differences between the sexes that are objectively conditioned and will remain valid in the future — will be revealed in the next crises.

From the perspective of the psychographic segmentation methodology, this study demonstrates a key practical implication: the proportional structure of psychographic groups within any population is not static. It responds measurably to acute societal stressors, and these responses are gender-differentiated in systematic and predictable ways. Communicators and marketers who rely on a single static psychographic reading of a population risk serious miscalibration during periods of societal stress — precisely when accurate targeting is most consequential.

Notes

[1] Basic characteristics of the groups: Seekers — most self-confident and risk-prone; strongly oriented toward experiencing emotions; feel comfortable in community. Members — avoid tension and conflict, seek comfort and ease; look for community presence; strive to verbalize a personal position. Solitary — do not accept the opinions of others, consider only their own opinion valid; not influenced by referents or majority opinion; community is not a value for them; convinced of their personal abilities. Bearings — most cautious and least self-confident of all, totally avoid any possible risk; their priority is the search for security; tend to conform to the opinions of others; experiencing emotions has very low importance for them.

[2] Data from Progress Consult for the period 2012–2014 are presented, but in reality the results from the agency's previous surveys in the period 2005–2011 showed the same structure of ratios. Data for the earlier period are not presented since during that period certain fine-tuning of the instrument for defining psychographic profiles was being carried out, so only results from surveys with absolute uniformity of the applied methodology are shown.

Bibliography

- Ambrosetti. (2021). *Headway 2023 — Mental Health Index: The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Mental Health*. Milano: The European House — Ambrosetti.
- Beauvoir, S. d. (1956). *The Second Sex*. London: Lowe and Brydone.
- Beck, U. (2013). *Risk Society: Towards a New Modernity*. Sofia: Kritika i Humanizum. [Original: Beck, U. (1986). *Risikogesellschaft: Auf dem Weg in eine andere Moderne*. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp.]
- Bourdieu, P. (1998). On male domination. *Le Monde diplomatique*. <https://mondediplo.com/On-male-domination>
- Connell, R. (1995). *Masculinities*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- CITUB — Confederation of Independent Trade Unions of Bulgaria. (16.09.2016). Position of CITUB. The development of the refugee and migration crisis is entering an extremely dangerous course for our country. <https://knsb-bg.org/pdf/2016/posizija-KNSB-september-2016f.pdf>
- Engels, F. (1884). *The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State*. <https://www.marxists.org/>
- Goffman, E. (1979). *Gender Advertisements*. New York: Harper & Row Publishers.
- Harris, C. B., & Jenkins, M. (2023). Gender Differences in Risk Assessment: Why do Women Take Fewer Risks than Men? Judgment and Decision Making. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/judgment-and-decision-making/>
- Koutelov, R. (2024). Information pressure on market entities and the Psychographic Profiles. In: *Economy, Society and Human Resources in the Challenge of Time* (pp. 27–38). Sofia: UNWE.
- Koutelov, R. (2024). Psychographic segmentation: the direct path of media and advertising to the audience. *Newmedia21*. <https://www.newmedia21.eu/>
- Kyuchukov, L. (2016). *The impact of the refugee crisis on Bulgarian society and Bulgarian politics: fears, but not hatred*. Sofia: Friedrich Ebert Foundation. <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/sofia/12571.pdf>
- MLSP — Ministry of Labor and Social Policy of Bulgaria. (2024). *Report on gender equality in Bulgaria for 2023*. Sofia: Ministry of Labor and Social Policy.
- Pallesen, S., & Andreassen, C. S. (2014). Social Network Site Addiction — An Overview. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 20, 4053–4061.
- Parliament of Bulgaria. (2025). *Chronology of the National Assembly*. <https://www.parliament.bg/bg/16>
- Parsons, T. (1991). *The Social System*. London: Routledge.
- Puzio, A. (2021). Why Is There Such A Gender Gap In COVID-19 Vaccination Rates? *FiveThirtyEight*. <https://fivethirtyeight.com/>
- Tannen, D. (2013). *You Just Don't Understand: Women and Men in Conversation*. New York: HarperCollins.
- Varbanova, V., Hens, N., & Beutels, P. (2024). Determinants of COVID-19 vaccination coverage in European and OECD countries. *Frontiers in Public Health*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/>
- West, C., & Zimmerman, D. H. (1987). Doing gender. *Gender and Society*, 1(2), 125–151.

About the Author

Rossen Koutelov is Doctor of Sociology (UNWE Sofia, 2025) and founder of Progress Consult (est. 1996), a Bulgarian marketing research and consulting agency. His doctoral dissertation, 'Psychographic Profiles and Consumer Behavior,' developed an original longitudinal methodology for psychographic segmentation validated through 13 nationally representative surveys (N=12,904, Bulgaria 2013–2023), identifying four stable psychographic groups — Seekers, Members, Solitary, and Bearings.

This paper demonstrates one of the central empirical findings of that methodology: that the proportional shares of psychographic groups respond systematically and in a gender-differentiated manner to acute societal stressors — a finding with significant implications for communication strategy and behavioral prediction.

Contact / Further work: www.progressconsult.com

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